

	FR1-IMGT (1-26)	CDR1-IMGT (27-38)	FR2-IMGT (39-55)	CDR2-IMGT (56-65)	FR3-IMGT (66-104)	CDR3-IMGT (105-117)	FR4-IMGT (118-128)	Closest germline	% identity
IgG1-2G	EEKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLTCVGS	GFDF...SDNS	FSWVRQAPGKGLEWVAA	IATGDYDGGT	FYTDSVK.GRFTISSDSSQNTAYLQMNTLRAEDTARYYC	ATTPLRLTIAVAIAVIGVAGYRPVMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-6*01	94.56
IgG1-4D	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLSCVGS	GFTF...SSTY	INWVRQAPGKGLEWLAT	LTSS..GSVT	NYADSVK.GRSDISRDNQNTAWLQMNSLRTEDTARYYC	AIGYIEGSATYYGMDL	WPGVQVVVSS	IGHV1-10*01	92.01
IgG1-5E	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLTLSCVGS	GFTF...SSIY	INWVRQAPGKGLEWLAA	ISNS..GSMT	YYADSVK.GRFTISRDNQNTAYVRVNSLRTETARYYC	ARCFYGGGCIYAGFYVMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-4*02	93.75
IgG1-5F	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSVRLSCVGS	GITF...TNTY	INWVRQAPGKGLWLAT	MTTV..GGVT	NYADSVK.GRFTISRDNQNTAYLQMNSLRTKDTARYYC	AIGYTGASATYYGMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-10*01	93.4
IgG1-7A	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSVRLSCVGS	GFTF...SSTY	INWVRQAPGKGLEWLAT	LTSS..ASVT	NYADSVK.GRFTISRDNQNTAYLQMNSLRTEDTARYYC	AIGYVGGSATYYGMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-10*01	90.97
IgG1-7E	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLSCVGS	GFTF...SSDF	MSWVRQAPGKGLEWLAC	ISNS..GDNT	YYADSVK.GRFTMSRDNQNTAYLQMSSLKTEDTALVYC	VRGCGGHALDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-4*02	90.97
IgG1-9D	EVKLVESGG.GLVQVGGSLRLSCVGS	GISF...SIYS	VNWRQAPGKGLEWLGS	IGRS..GTNT	WYADSVK.GRFTISRDNQNTAYLQMTSLRTEDTARYWC	EGSCSNCPSPSTVNL	WPGGVEVVISS	IGHV1-8*01	89.58
IgG1-11A	EEKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLSCVGS	GFTF...STYE	IIWVRQAPGKGLEWLAA	ISTR..GSSF	DYADSVK.GRFTINRDDSHTATLQMNTLGTEDTARYYC	TGGHRCYGLFGGCFWFGDYAMHL	WPGGVEVAVSS	IGHV1-14*01	92.36
IgG1-11B 11C 11D 12C	EEKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLSCVGS	GFDL...RRYG	VWVRQAPGKGLLESALF	IGSVSYLGST	YYADSVK.GRFTISRDDSQNTVYLQLNSLRTEDTARYYC	ARVGCYCNNGGSWYADRPVFMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-11*01	94.56
IgG1-11E	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLSCVGS	GFDL...RRYG	VWVRQAPGKGLLESALF	IGSVSYLGST	YYADSVK.GRFTISRDDSQNTVYLQLNSLRTEDTARYYC	ARVGCYCNNGGSWYADRPVFMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-11*01	94.22
IgG1-11F	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLSCVGS	GFDL...RRYG	VWVRQAPGKGLLESALF	IGSVSYLGST	YYADSVK.GRFTISRDDSQNTVYLQLISLRTEDTARYYC	ARVGCYCNNGGSWYADRPVFMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-11*01	93.2
IgG1-12B 12D	EVKLVESGG.GLVQPGGSLRLSCVGS	GFDL...RRYG	VWVRQAPGKGLLESALF	IGSVSYLGST	YYADSVK.GRFTISRDDSQNTVYLQLNSLRTEDTARYYC	ARVGCYCNNGGSWYADRPVFMDL	WPGGVEVVVSS	IGHV1-11*01	94.56
IgLC-κ-2G	AIVLTQTPLPLSVSPGEPASISCRSG	QSLLHT.DGANY	LNWYLQKPGRSPQLLIY	YA.....T	NRASGVP.DRFTGSG..SGTDFTLKISRVEAEDVGVFYC	FLSLQSPYG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-10*02	93.54
IgLC-λ-4D	SYELTQPSS.ESVALGKTAKITCSGD	LLD.....KKY	TQWYQKPGQAPLLVIY	KD.....S	ERPSGIP.ERFSGSS..SGKTATLSITGAQAEDAEDYIC	QSADNIHNVI	FGGGTHLTVL	IGLV3-3*01	96.42
IgLC-λ-5E	SYELTQPSS.ESVALGNTAKITCSGD	LLD.....AKY	TMVEKRGGQAPRLLIY	KD.....S	ERPSGIP.ERFSGSS..SGKTATLTITGAQAEDAEDYIC	QSADSLDSVP	FGGGTHLSVL	IGLV3-3*01	87.81
IgLC-λ-5F	SYELTQPSS.ESVALGNTAKITCSGD	LLD.....AKY	TQWYQKSGQAPLLLIY	KD.....T	ERPSGIP.ERFSGSS..SGKTATLTITGAQAEDAEDYIC	QSADRIDNVP	FGGGTHLTVP	IGLV3-3*01	97.49
IgLC-λ-7A 7E	SYEVTQPSS.ESVALGNTAKITCSGD	LLD.....KKY	TQWYQKPGQAPLLLIY	KD.....S	ERPSGIP.ERFSGSN..SGKTATLTITGAQAEDAEDYIC	QSADNIHNVI	FGGGTHLTVP	IGLV3-3*01	96.77
IgLC-λ-9D	SYELTQPAS.ESVALGNTAKITCSGD	LVD.....KTG	TRWYQKPGQAPLLLIY	ND.....S	ERPSGIP.ERFSGSM..SWRTATLTITGAQAEDAEDYIC	RSPDISGHLV	FGGGTHLTVL	IGLV3-3*02	93.55
IgLC-κ-11A	AIVLTQTPLSLSVSPGEPASISCRSS	LTLPT..NGAFG	KKEKSRNQASLHSSLSM	RL.....P	TGPLGSH.FPFSGSG..SGTDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	QFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	70.79
IgLC-κ-11B	AIVLTQTPLSLSVSPGEPASISCRSS	QSRCRR.MEHLR	KKRGEQKPGQSPQLLIY	EA.....T	NRASGVP.YPLSGSG..SGTDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	QFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	68.42
IgLC-κ-11C	AIVLTQTPLSLSVSPGEPASISCRSS	QSDAA..DEWNI	EKGKQKPGQSPQLLIY	EA.....T	NRASGVP.DRFSGSG..SGTDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	QFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	69.1
IgLC-κ-11D	AIQLTQSPASLAASLGDTVSITWRAS	QSDAAD.EWSLW	DKGWKKKPGQSPQLLIY	EA.....T	NRASGVP.FPFSGSG..SGTDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	RQFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	67.01
IgLC-κ-11E	AIVLTQTPLSLSVSPGEPASISCRSS	ASDAA..DEPYR	PKKRRNRVSTLLIYE	AT.....N	RASGVPS.LRKGSG..SGFDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	QFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	67.01
IgLC-κ-11F	AIVLTQTPLSLSVSPGEPASISCRSS	AHLTL..PTNGH	WQKRRNRVSTAPDLY	GY.....Q	QGLWGPI.PRFSGSG..SGTDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	QFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	68.04
IgLC-κ-12C	AIVLTQTPLSLSVSPGEPASISCRST	SDAADE.WRFDN	KKKGAETRPVSTAPDLY	GY.....Q	QGLWGPS.PPFSGSG..SGSDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	QFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	68.04
IgLC-κ-12D	AIVLTQTPLSLSVSPGEPASISCRSS	QSRCR..RMEAI	CHEYQKPGQSPQLLIY	EA.....T	NRASGVP.DRFSGSG..SGTDFTLKINRVEAEDAGVYYC	QFKEFPRG	FGAGTKLELK	IGKV2-13*02	71.93

Table S4. Protein display of in-frame IGV for sequenced single cell pair IGH and IGLC genes using IMGT unique numbering. Sequences from single sorted B cells were compared to standardized representations of the amino acid sequences of the V-DOMAINS, including framework regions (FR1-IMGT, FR2-IMGT, FR3-IMGT, FR4-IMGT) and complementarity determining regions (CDR1-IMGT, CDR2-IMGT, CDR3-IMGT), enabling comparison to, and calculation of distance from, nearest germline sequences. Sequences in **bold** were successfully expressed.